

PRINCIPLES FOR FORMING BASIC COMPETENCIES IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article reveals the essence, methods and effectiveness of the basis for the formation of basic competencies in increasing the work efficiency of a future primary school teacher, the content of the concept of professional competence, why basic competencies and their advantages are necessary, discussed the possibilities of using basic competencies in the process of higher education, the attention paid competency-based approach in our republic and cases of its implementation.*

Keywords: *teacher, student, basic competence, integrative approach, professional competence, pedagogical skill, education, upbringing, society, lesson, mastery, methodology, tool, knowledge, skill, qualification.*

INTRODUCTION

Studying advanced foreign experience in the context of the constantly changing methodological competence of future primary school teachers in our country, it is necessary to develop technology, didactic foundations for the development of their methodological competence in a higher educational institution, determine pedagogical conditions, content and structure, improvement criteria and levels of formation, form, method, means, model, indicators of effectiveness and quality of training. increase, and also, in a pedagogical university, the development of theoretical and practical foundations for the development of methodological competence among future primary school teachers is becoming important.

Currently, the socio-economic, political-spiritual, cultural and educational changes taking place in our republic and the corresponding system of lifelong education and training are being radically updated. In particular, the training of modern personnel is becoming more relevant than ever. Without pedagogical innovations it is impossible to prepare such modern personnel.

Today, the main goal of higher education is to educate the younger generation, teach them their profession, and make them mentally and spiritually mature. Based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" [1], life itself requires a new development of the content and means of education. This factor requires that the components of the educational process appear in a new order. In this organizational and pedagogical process, following new principles in accordance with the laws and principles of education, the emergence of teaching methods, improving teaching aids, especially integrative forms of teacher skills in organizing education, are being implemented on a large scale. A certain part of these changes arose as a composition of competency-based approaches, and the other part appeared on the basis of the pedagogical experience of scientists from developed countries in the global education system.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The expected result in the process of training students in pedagogical higher educational institutions is formed in the form of requirements for mastering basic educational programs, presented through general cultural, general professional and professional competencies. The state educational standards also define the profile (special) competence of the future teacher, which is an important organizer of the professional competence of the teacher. Currently, this is one of the little-studied problems. One of these issues is the definition of a competency-based approach to the development of professional competencies among future primary school teachers and the development of its structural model in accordance with the main provisions of state educational standards. To determine the professional competence of a future primary school teacher, we will focus on some studies examining this concept.

In studies where professional competence is studied as a pedagogical problem, the characteristics of the teacher are mainly analyzed.

V.I. Bidenko characterized the concept of “professional competence” as follows:

- have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities necessary to work in the specialty, have signs of independence and flexibility at the same time while partially solving professional problems;

- development of cooperation with colleagues in a professional interpersonal environment;
- structure for developing standards, including performance criteria (quality indicator), scope and required knowledge;

- effective use of abilities that allow you to effectively carry out professional activities in accordance with the requirements of the employer;

- a complex combination of knowledge, characteristics and skills that allow a person to successfully perform work in a modern work environment [2, 72].

To summarize the above, V.I. Bidenko understands by professional competence the readiness and ability to act in accordance with the requirements of the activity, independently solve issues and problems and at the same time be able to evaluate the results of one’s activities, that is, relevant skills and technical methods.

According to O.V. Khovov, professional competence is not only competence, that is, professional competence as work experience, skills and knowledge, but also social-communicative and individual abilities that ensure independence in professional activities [5].

Yu.G. Tatur and V.E. The Medvedevs define the competence of a future specialist as the desire and ability to demonstrate their potential (knowledge, skills, experience, personal qualities, etc.). He defined it as the willingness to use all one’s capabilities (knowledge, skills, experience and personal qualities), to be able to work successfully in any field and to be aware of one’s responsibility for the result. According to G.A. Larionova, the structure of readiness includes a complex of practical knowledge and characteristics that ensure a person’s entry into activity. Preparation for work is complex and consists of two components - operational (knowledge and skills) and personal (instruction, work orientation, professional motivational characteristics, a system of habits and relationships, emotional-volitional functions, professionally important human qualities). [3, 171].

Determining what competencies a specialist has, that is, what method of activity he can master, what he can do, what he is ready for, is called a competent approach. One of the conceptually important ways to manage the quality of training of graduates of a higher educational

institution is the implementation of a competent approach to modernizing the content of vocational education.

Among Uzbek scientists Abdullaeva B.S. [3], Gulomov A [6], Nematov O', Rozimuhammad B [7], Ziyamuhammadov B [8], Abdullaeva Sh. expressed their opinion on the possibilities.

DISCUSSION

A modern future primary school teacher must be advanced in all aspects, have deep knowledge of his subject, have teaching skills, love children, know the problem in practice and find ways to solve the problem.

Analyzing the requirements for the modern future primary school teacher, the need to form and educate patriotic individuals who are able to think independently, think correctly, and perform acceptable work,” we considered it permissible to quote his opinion [2]

Competence is the quality of a person who has deep, comprehensive knowledge in a particular field and is therefore considered reliable and trustworthy.

Competence is one of the constantly evolving qualities of a person, the ability to solve problems in real life situations, the ability to mobilize one’s knowledge, educational and life experience, values and interests.

In the analysis of foreign literature, competence means “possessor of deep knowledge”, “ability to solve complex problems”, “ability to carry out real activities at the moment”. [9]

E. F. Zeer defines important competencies as personal qualities and abilities necessary for a person to adapt to various professional activities and perform certain tasks for the purpose of effective activity. Within the framework of critical competencies, four subgroups are considered separately. These are: professional direction; professional competence; professional quality; professionally important psychophysiological characteristics.

Pedagogical competence is the personal capabilities of the teacher, his skills (knowledge and experience), solving problems based on his knowledge and skills in a certain area.

According to R.V. Ovcharova, pedagogical competence is the sum of a person’s psychological qualities (character, temperament, etc.).

Along with the term “professional competence”, scientific and pedagogical literature uses similar terms such as “professionalism”, “professional skill”, “qualification”, “master of his profession”.

Today, instead of the term “professionalism,” the concept of “competence” is often used. The first concept reflects only certain professional skills and qualifications. The second concept of “competence” means a stock of skills, a base.

Definitions of professional competence have arisen in different ways:

- ability to perform a certain job function;
- human qualities, such as “qualification”, “skill” (A.K. Makarova);
- level of professional education;
- a person’s experience and individuality, his desire to improve his knowledge and skills, his creative approach to work and responsibility for his work (B.S. Gershunsky)
- acquisition of professional knowledge, qualifications and skills (O.A. Abdudukusov, Kh.F. Rashidov);
- knowledge, skills, originality and ability to organize educational processes of the individual (V.A. Sitarov) [10]

- social orientation of experience, knowledge, results of a person's practical activity towards a specific goal; unique qualities and competencies of a person, such as the effective application of professional knowledge in life (L. N. Ponamarov) [9]

Professional competence is achieved by performing multifaceted functions, relying on a range of social knowledge within the framework of one professional activity, and expanding the types of activities.

The problem of increasing the level of professional competence of a future teacher, who has the ability to think freely and actively, model the educational process, develop and implement new ideas and technologies for teaching and upbringing, is a modern socio-economic problem that is relevant in these circumstances.

The main conditions for the development of professional competence of future teachers are:

1) organizational and managerial (curriculum, schedule of the educational process, class schedule, development of criteria for determining the level of competence, material and technical planning of the educational process);

2) educational and methodological (selection of lesson content, integration of different courses, identification of leading ideas);

3) technological (control and evaluation, organization of active forms of learning, identification of knowledge groups within the competence, application of innovative technologies);

4) psychological and pedagogical (diagnosis of student development, stimulation of motivation to learn, determination of competence criteria, orientation of students to joint work). The structure of the future teacher's professional competence is determined through his pedagogical skills, and skills (knowledge based on theoretical knowledge and focused on solving pedagogical problems) are determined through a set of gradually developing actions.

RESULTS

The qualification requirements establish the following requirements for a future primary school teacher in terms of teaching activities:

- have systematic knowledge related to worldview; know the basics of the humanities and natural sciences, current issues of current public policy, be able to independently analyze social problems and processes;

- have a comprehensive understanding of the processes and events occurring in nature and society, acquire knowledge about the development of nature and society and be able to use them in life and in their profession on a modern scientific basis;

- know the legal and moral criteria that determine a person's attitude towards another person, towards society, towards the environment, and be able to take them into account in professional activities;

- possesses knowledge of methods of collecting, storing, processing and using information and is able to make independent decisions in his professional activities;

pedagogical design of the educational process in the electronic information educational environment;

- have competitive general professional training in the relevant undergraduate specialty;

- able to independently acquire new knowledge, work on oneself and organize work on a scientific basis;

- having mastered one foreign language at the level of freedom of speech;
- it is determined that he must have a scientific imagination and beliefs about a healthy lifestyle and the need to adhere to it, as well as physical training and skills.

In addition, the future primary school teacher must find effective forms and methods of teaching, strengthen the activities of educational and methodological training, adjust the forms, methods and means of organizing classes in special subjects in the formation of his professional competence, he must be able to choose the right methods and means.

In our opinion, a future primary school teacher must be able to apply in practice the knowledge acquired in the specialty, and also have professional qualities that are important for a teacher (self-development, desire for new things) or, in other words, must have professional competence.

The main conditions for the development of professional competence of future teachers are:

1) organizational and managerial (curriculum, schedule of the educational process, class schedule, development of criteria for determining the level of competence, logistics of the educational process);

2) educational and methodological (selection of lesson content, integration of different courses, identification of leading ideas);

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The structure of the future teacher's professional competence is determined through his pedagogical skills, and skills (knowledge based on theoretical knowledge and focused on solving pedagogical problems) are determined through a set of gradually developing actions.

CONCLUSION

Today, in the process of implementing the requirements of the Law "On Education" [1], the training of highly qualified teaching staff is put on the agenda as an important problem.

Thus, based on these requirements, one of the pressing problems is the preparation of educated, independent thinkers, creative seekers, highly qualified, cultural workers in various industries. Among the conditions that guarantee the maturation of an individual according to a new model recognized by law, his becoming the owner of deep knowledge, the teacher's competence in applying his professional and methodological competence in educational processes, as if his own methods and rules of psychology are insufficient.

Accordingly, the younger generation requires developmental trends during periods of study to study how new teaching technologies can be mastered by the student and how they affect his mental and intellectual abilities, as well as a combination of psychological methods with didactic methods.

To do this, the future teacher is required to have a high level of socio-psychological competence associated with methodological competence, especially the ability to correctly assess the psychology of the student and teacher in various conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 23, 2020 No. ORQ-637. Education Act".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. 5712 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030."
3. Bidenko V.I. Identification of the composition of competencies of university graduates as a necessary stage in the design of a new generation of state educational institutions. - M. - 2006. - 72 p.
4. Larionova G. A. Competencies in the professional training of university students: knowledge, actions, activities, self-determination: monograph. - Chelyabinsk. – 2004. – 171 p.
5. Muslimov N.A., Usmonboeva M.Kh., Sayfurov D.M., Toraev A.B. Innovative educational technologies / – T.: Sano Standard Publishing House, 2015. – P. 81.
6. Larionova G. A. Competencies in the professional training of university students: knowledge, actions, activities, self-determination: monograph. - Chelyabinsk. – 2004. – 171 p.
7. Makhmudov A.Kh. Didactic aspects of the competency-based approach in the education system // Materials of the Republican scientific and practical conference on the topic "The importance of innovative technologies in improving the professional skills of teachers." - Tashkent. - 2012. P. 44-47.
8. Khovov O.V. Professional competence // Encyclopedia of professional education: In 3 volumes - M.: APO. - 1998.-T.1. -P.454- 455.
9. Karimova M. and Tuychieva R. (2019). Pedagogical foundations of preparing students for professional, moral and educational functions. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(10), 311-317.
10. Khaitboevich B. B. (2020). Some features of protecting students from the threat of malicious information in the educational process. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8(10), 69-72.